

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D3.5 Report on the modelling for thermo-hydraulic and ratcheting behaviours

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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targasonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
D	Deliverable
FEM	Finite Element Model
F-ISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
PU	Public
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

This report briefly explains the activities that, in relation to modelling the thermohydraulic behaviour of the storage tank, have been performed up to now in WP3. Thermal ratcheting study was already included in D3.3, so it is not included here.

In this report the simulation models of each partner participating in this activity are briefly explained. All the models have been validated in previous studies, with a pebble bed configuration. The experimental results obtained at MicroSol facility at different working conditions have been used to modify/validate/improve the specific models in order to consider a structured filler bed, like POLYPHEM TES approach is. A comparison between models and their results is presented at the end of this report.

2. CEA SIMULATION MODEL

CEA has a numerical model for packed bed dual-media thermocline thermal energy storage. This model has been adapted and modified to be relevant for POLYPHEM configuration, i.e., for a structured dual-media thermocline thermal energy storage.

2.1 PHYSICAL APPROACH

The global geometry and the related physical phenomenon taken into account in the CEA numerical model are illustrated in **Figure 1**:

- The storage tank is divided in 3 distinct zones, i.e. purely liquid top and bottom plenums and the filler bed inside the tank's shell;
- The top and bottom purely liquid plenums are treated as zones of perfect mixing to take into account the influence of the fluid distribution systems;
- The filler bed is characterized by conduction inside the concrete and the thermal oil, convection between the concrete and the thermal oil, thermal losses with the ambient and pressure drop.

Figure 1: Geometry and physical phenomena considered in the CEA numerical model

2.1.1 Filler Bed

The model for the Filler Bed is derived from previously published model based on two energy equations using the following assumptions:

- Fluid and solid are considered separately by a dedicated energy equation;
- The fluid velocity and the temperature evolutions are considered only in the tank axis direction, thus the governing equations are one-dimensional, implying a transversal homogeneity of the oil and rocks temperatures;
- The solid filler is considered as a continuous, homogeneous and isotropic porous medium;
- The properties of the filler are independent of the temperature;
- Filler temperature is assumed to be homogeneous inside each solid volume;
- The distributors are not included in the computational domain, the conditions of uniform velocity and temperature are considered at the inlet of the storage. This condition is equivalent to a storage tank with well-designed distributors;
- Stand-by mode behaviour, i.e. when fluid mass flux is equal to zero, is defined by a single equation.

With the above assumptions and taking into account the heat conduction in the oil and in the solid bed and the heat losses from the tank to the ambient, the governing equations can be written as follows whenever there is a non-zero oil flow:

$$\text{Liquid HTF: } \varepsilon \rho_f c_{p,f} \left[\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k_f \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right) + h_{s,f} (T_s - T_f) - h_{ext} (T_f - T_{ext}) \quad \text{Eq.(1)}$$

$$\text{Solid concrete: } (1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s c_{p,s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = k_s \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial x^2} + h_{s,f} (T_f - T_s) \quad \text{Eq.(2)}$$

When fluid mass flux is equal to zero, solid and fluid temperatures are assumed to be the same and thermal behaviour inside the storage tank is treated using a single equation:

$$\text{Stand-by: } \rho c_p)_{mean} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_{mean} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - h_{ext} (T - T_{ext}) \quad \text{Eq.(3)}$$

In the previous equations, ε is the solid bed porosity, v is the fluid velocity inside the solid bed, $h_{s,f}$ is the volumetric heat transfer coefficient (in $\text{W}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{K}$) between the thermal oil and the solid bed and h_{ext} is the volumetric heat transfer coefficient (in $\text{W}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{K}$) with the ambient. The subscripts “f”, “s” and “ext” refer to heat transfer fluid, concrete and ambient, respectively.

The configuration considered in POLYPHEM is a structured dual-media thermocline with the thermal oil circulating in pipe-like holes in the concrete, from inlet to outlet of the storage. As a first glance, the fluid flow inside the pipes is laminar due to the Reynolds number, Re , based on mass flow rate and pipe diameter. However, even if the inner surface condition of the concrete channels is not well known, it seems extremely rough. Thus, the choice of a relevant correlation for the convective heat transfer (HTC) between the concrete and the thermal oil to be implemented in Eq. (1) is not so straightforward. In this study, the Wakao’s correlation has been used:

$$Nu = 2 + 1.1 Re_{f,sup}^{0.6} Pr_f^{1/3} \quad \text{Eq.(4)}$$

Where $Re_{f,sup}$ is the superficial oil Reynolds number defined as

$$Re_{f,sup} = \frac{\dot{m} D_r}{\mu_f \frac{\pi D_{tank}^2}{4}} \quad \text{Eq.(5)}$$

The heat loss heat transfer coefficient, h_{ext} , is calculated from the thermal resistance of the insulation layer $R_{cond,insulation}$, the thermal resistance due to convection with ambient $R_{conv ext}$ and the thermal resistance due to internal convection $R_{conv int}$. The calculation of $R_{conv int}$ is based on the volumetric heat transfer coefficient $h_{s,f}$.

In all previous equations, thermo-physical properties (density, thermal conductivity, specific heat and dynamic viscosity) are temperature-dependent for the HTF and considered constant for solid filler.

The boundary conditions are presented here for the charge process only. At the inlet of the storage tank, hot fluid at given velocity and temperature is injected:

$$v_L = v_{inlet}; \quad T_f|_L = T_{inlet}; \quad (\partial T_s / \partial z)_L = 0 \quad \text{Eq.(6)}$$

At the outlet of the storage tank, the boundary conditions are given as follows:

$$(\partial T_s / \partial z)_{x=0} = (\partial T_f / \partial z)_{x=0} = 0 \quad \text{Eq.(7)}$$

In discharge process, due to reverse fluid flow, the boundary conditions are similar with inversion between bottom and top (inlet at the tank bottom) with different inlet velocity and temperature.

In each charge or discharge process, temperature profiles for the solid bed and the fluid are given as initial conditions:

$$\begin{cases} T_f(t = 0, x) = T_{f,0}(x) \\ T_s(t = 0) = T_{s,0}(x) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq.(8)}$$

In successive multiple charge/discharge configuration, the temperature profiles at the end of a cycle is taken as initial conditions of the next cycle.

2.1.2 Top and bottom liquid plenums

The Filler Bed is enclosed at its upper and bottom sides by purely liquid plenums in which the fluid distribution is made. Those plenums have being considered and simulated as they influence the storage behaviour by adding time delay between the tank inlet and the inlet of the Filler Bed.

Basically, the top and bottom liquid plenum are integrated into the CEA model with the following assumptions:

- Top and bottom purely liquid volumes are treated as perfect mixing volumes;
- The effective volume of the top and bottom plenums considered for the simulation are “fitted” using experimental results;
- Currently, those purely liquid volumes are only considered at the inlet, i.e. top plenum in charge and bottom plenum in discharge. Due to specific geometry and behaviour of the fluid distribution system, the effective volume considered in the model may differ in charge and in discharge, i.e., at the inlet and the outlet.

2.2 APPLYING MODEL TO POLYPHEM

The first step consisted in applying the model on some typical experimental tests in charge and discharge in order to determine and adapt some parameters values. Currently, such approach is required since we simulate a full 3D geometry with specificities with a simplified 1D model. In addition, the configuration of the POLYPHEM prototype includes some elements that are not finely known or that deviate from simple 1D approach, such as the fluid flow conditions inside the concrete channels, the transverse fluid and temperature homogeneities, the surface quality of the concrete channels, etc.

As a result of this preliminary study, a common set of parameters and properties to be considered in the numerical model has been defined for charge and discharge, respectively. These values are presented in **Table 1**.

Filler bed
HTF volume: 0.879 m³
Eff. porosity: 33.0%

$(D, H)_{\text{tank}} = (1.2 \text{ m}; 2.6 \text{ m})$
 $e_{\text{wall}} = 0 \text{ cm}$

$H_{\text{bottom_plenum}} = 0 \text{ cm}$ in discharge
 $H_{\text{top_plenum}} = 10 \text{ cm}$ in charge

Porosity = 33%
Thermal oil DBT, physical properties depend on temperature

HTC fluid/concrete:
 $Nu = Nu_{\text{WAKAO}}$

HTC heat loss:
 $Nu = Nu_{\text{calculated}}/2$

- Concrete:
- 3105 kg/m³
 - 1300 J/kg.K (+ 20% to initially considered)

Table 1: Set of parameters used for CEA simulations

2.2.1 Numerical/experimental comparison in Charge

The set of parameters defined in the **Table 1** is well suitable for most of experimental test in charge, as illustrated in **Figure 2** with different mass flow rates and temperature levels and differences. Circular markers lines are for experimental data at MicroSol test facility, continuous lines for liquid temperature and discontinuous lines for solid temperatures. A good agreement is observed, on the shape of the axial temperature profile and its temporal displacement.

(a) 0.4 kg/s

(b) 0.45 kg/s

(c) 0.2 kg/s

(d) 0.3 kg/s

Figure 2: Numerical/experimental comparison in charge with good agreement with the set of parameters defined in Table 1; (a): 08/03/2021 test; (b): 26/03/2021 test; (c): 01/04/2021 test; (d): 13/04/2021 test; (e): 15/04/2021 test; (f): 16/04/2021 test

In some conditions, illustrated in **Figure 3**, the volume of the inlet plenum has to be neglected to obtain a good agreement between numerical predictions and experimental data. This is the case for oil flow rate lower than 0.2kg/s and higher than 0.6 kg/s. This may be related to different behaviours in the liquid plenums and in the fluid distribution system depending of the HTF flow rates.

Figure 3: Numerical/experimental comparison in charge with necessary modification of the set of parameters defined in Table 1; (a) and (b): 31/03/2021 test; (c) and (d): 07/04/2021 test; (e) and (f): 04/05/2021 test

2.2.2 Numerical/experimental comparison in Discharge

The same kind of results is obtained when discharging as illustrated in Figure 4 and Figure 5. Most of the tests in discharge can be successfully simulated with the common set of parameters defined in Table 1, but some tests require specific adaptation of some parameters. In those cases, the Nusselt number (Nu) has to be highly increased and an additional bottom inlet plenum added.

(e) 0.9 kg/s

Figure 4: Numerical/experimental comparison in discharge with good agreement with the set of parameters defined in Table 1; (a): 10/03/2021 test; (b): 12/03/2021 test; (c): 22/03/2021 test; (d): 23/03/2021 test; (e): 31/03/2021 test

0.3 kg/s (a) Table 1

(b) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$

(c) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$ AND $H_{bottom}=5$ cm

0.2 kg/s (d) Table 1

(e) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$

(f) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$ AND $H_{bottom}=5$ cm

0.2 kg/s (g) Table 1

(h) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$

(i) with $3 * Nu_{Wakao}$ AND $H_{bottom}=5$ cm

Figure 5: Numerical/experimental comparison in discharge with necessary modification of the set of parameters defined in Table 1; (a), (b) and (c): 14/04/2021 test; (d), (e) and (f): 20/04/2021 test; (g); (h) and (i): 22/04/2021 test

2.2.3 Simulation Results in Standby

Two standby tests have been simulated and results are presented in **Figure 6**. A good agreement is obtained for 16 h standby from an initially almost axially uniform tank (**Figure 6 (a)**). The simulation of a 48 h standby from an initially non uniform tank shows good qualitative agreement but less quantitative agreement (**Figure 6 (b)**).

Figure 6: Numerical/experimental comparison in standby tests; (a): 15-16/04/2021 test; (b): 16-18/04/2021 test

2.2.4 Conclusions

A comparison between the POLYPHEM experimental results and the numerical prediction with the CEA model for dual-media thermocline thermal energy storage has been performed on a large set of experimental tests.

Main conclusions and comments can be expressed as follows:

- Numerical simulations globally show good agreement with the experimental data on large ranges of mass flow rates and temperature conditions whenever the plenum that first faces the HTF is taken into account and heat transfer coefficient HTF-solid has to be appropriately modified.
- The influence of this inlet fluid distribution zone is to give some inertia to the system, so, mainly, delaying the temperature profile advance.
- This influence seems to be negligible when it is relatively small (bottom plenum in discharge) or at high mass flows –since the flow seems not to see the plenum–.
- The Wakao correlation for the Nusselt number for the heat transfer between the oil and the solid in charge seems to fit pretty well the experimental results.
- At discharge the heat transfer coefficient has to be increased to fix experimental data with mass flows below 0.4 kg/s.
- At charge for low mass flow (0.1 kg/s) the top plenum seems to have no influence.
- The last two points may indicate that buoyance forces play a non-negligible role in the thermohydraulic behaviour of the storage tank.

3. F-ISE SIMULATION MODEL

A stratified single-tank thermal energy storage model, developed at Fraunhofer ISE and implemented in the in-house simulation software ColSim CSP, was adapted to the required conditions of the POLYPHEM project. The model incorporates heat exchange between the working fluid, the filler material and the tank walls, including transient axial conduction in the tank wall and heat loss to the surroundings.

3.1 PHYSICAL APPROACH

The model, in general, is based on a finite volume approach (Seubert et al. 2014). Some assumptions have been made to simplify the solution:

- One-dimensional discretization of the domain
- Detailed solution only of the energy equation

This model solves energy equations in one dimension. It can be categorized in 3 phases: fluid, solid, walls. While for the solid phase Eq.(2) is used, for the fluid phase:

$$\varepsilon \rho_f c_{p_f} \left(\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k_f \frac{dT_f}{dx} \right) + h_{s-f} A_s (T_s - T_f) \quad \text{Eq.(9)}$$

And for the wall:

$$\rho_w c_{p_w} \frac{\partial T_w}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k_w \frac{dT_w}{dx} \right) + h_{w,int} A_{w,int} (T_f - T_w) + h_{w,ext} A_{w,ext} (T_{ext} - T_w) \quad \text{Eq.(10)}$$

Where subscript w refers to wall. h (W/m²K) is the corresponding heat transfer coefficient and A refers to area. ρ , c_p , ε and k are density, specific heat capacity, porosity, and thermal conductivity respectively. Temperature dependent fluid properties are considered and are updated at each time step during the simulation while solid properties are considered constant. The heat transfer between HTF and solid, h_{s-f} , takes into account the convection heat transfer between thermal oil/concrete filler as well as thermal conduction inside the filler material. This convection heat transfer coefficient can be derived from different Nusselt number (Nu) correlations. Comparing the values obtained for the Nu with the working conditions imposed on the charging process on the 26/03/2021 at MicroSol facility using Gnielinski and Mills correlations, no major difference is observed between them, so the correlation by Gnielinski is considered in all simulations presented here.

Heat losses from the tank to ambient are derived by modelling thermal resistances (R) as below.

$$h_{w,int} A_{w,int} = \frac{1}{R_{conv,int} + R_{cond,wall}} \quad \text{Eq.(11)}$$

$$h_{w,ext} A_{w,ext} = \frac{1}{R_{conv,ext} + R_{cond,insulation}} \quad \text{Eq.(12)}$$

The same boundary conditions as for CEA model are taken into account, i.e.:

$$v = v_{inlet}; \quad T_f|_L = T_{inlet}; \quad (\partial T_s / \partial x)_L = (\partial T_w / \partial x)_L = 0 \quad \text{Eq.(13)}$$

$$(\partial T_s / \partial x)_{x=0} = (\partial T_f / \partial x)_{x=0} = (\partial T_w / \partial x)_{x=0} = 0 \quad \text{Eq.(14)}$$

3.1 APPLYING MODEL TO POLYPHEM

In order to simulate the behaviour of POLYPHEM prototype storage and to compare the results with experiments, two different approaches have been followed:

1. Modelling complete storage tank (**Figure 7 (a)**)
2. Modelling TES zone only (**Figure 7 (b)**)

Initial temperature condition and inlet boundary conditions (mass flow rate, temperature) are taken from the available experimental data.

Figure 7: Schemes considered for modelling; (a):Storage tank; (b):TES Zone

Table 2: List of parameters used for modelling dual-media region or TES zone and full Storage Tank

ID	Parameter	Values TES zone	Values Storage Tank	Unit
1	Diameter of tank	1.276	1.276	m
2	Height of tank	2.5	2.85	m
3	Volume of storage	3.197	3.644	m ³
4	Porosity	0.443	0.512	-
5	Wall thickness	0.008	0.008	m
6	Conductivity of wall	30	30	W/m-K
7	Cp of wall	500	500	J/kg-K
8	Density of wall	8000	8000	kg/m ³
9	Insulation thickness	0.255	0.255	m
10	Conductivity of insulation	0.086	0.086	W/m-K
11	Ambient temperature	15	15	°C

3.1.1 Modelling TES zone only: Numerical/experimental comparison

In this approach, the additional top and bottom liquid plenums are not considered. Therefore, only the dual media region is considered in the simulation domain. Uniform 1D fluid flow distribution is assumed inside this domain with no radial temperature gradient inside the storage. Heat transfer coefficient between thermal oil and concrete filler material is calculated based on Nu correlation given by Gnielinski. The following modification of the Nu number value has to be considered for the simulations presented here in order to fit experimental data:

Table 3: Parameter modification for modelling dual-media region (TES zone only)

Charge	$Nu_{\text{modified}} = Nu * 3$
Discharge	$Nu_{\text{modified}} = Nu * 4$

This modification can be partially explained by non-uniform geometry inside dual-media region (there are purely liquid zones in between each filler baskets, and also between tank walls and filler baskets) and the influence this may have in the heat transfer and fluid flow behaviours. Except Nusselt number modification in **Table 3** to calculate heat transfer, all other parameters in **Table 2** are considered based on the dual media region.

3.1.1.1 Simulation Results in Charge

The following figures show the comparison between the experimental data (continuous lines) and the simulated temperature evolution (++ lines) at the centre of the storage at different height and time steps.

Figure 8: Charge processes (a) from 180°C to 250°C (25.03.21); (b) from 180°C to 250°C (15.04.21); (c) from 180°C to 250°C (26.03.21); (d) from 180°C to 250°C (07.04.21)

Simulation results are in close agreement with experimental results in terms of thermocline region velocity and profile inside the storage, whenever the Nusselt number is modified as $Nu_{\text{modified}} = Nu \cdot 3$ for all charge.

In **Figure 8 (c) and (d)** at the lowest and highest temperatures, some discrepancies between experimental and simulation temperature profiles are observed to slightly increase over time. Pure liquid zones between each basket can be clearly identified in the experimental data by waves and ridges. These pure liquid zones and their specific thermohydraulic behaviour could be the reason of the above mentioned discrepancies.

3.1.1.1 Simulation Results in Discharge

According to **Figure 9**, simulation results are in good agreement with experimental ones in terms of discharge duration. To model heat transfer between oil and concrete brick, it is required to apply a different modification rule than the one applied for charge simulations, which explains that storage has different behaviour for charge and discharge cycles. It is necessary to impose $Nu_{\text{modified}} = Nu \cdot 4$ for all discharge simulations.

Figure 9: Discharge processes (a) from 250°C to 130°C (20.04.21); (b) from 250°C to 130°C (31.03.21), (c) from 180°C to 110°C (12.03.21); (d) from 180°C to 110°C (23.03.21)

In the above figures, the simulated thicknesses of the thermocline region are a little larger than the ones obtained experimentally. In addition to that, this mismatch is observed to be slightly larger at the top of the tank. The following reasons could be explained such behaviour:

- A different hydraulic structure of storage at inlet/outlet
- 1D flow behaviour simplification in simulation

- Heat transfer surface area between thermal oil and concrete bricks might be different that the one assumed
- Experimental discharge run initialized with already existing temperature stratification profile (while simulation started from uniform temperature).

3.1.2 Modelling Storage Tank: Numerical/experimental comparison

Under this approach it is necessary to take into account the heat capacity of the flange and inlet/outlet manifolds and the oil in the top and bottom plenums by increasing the overall storage capacity by 20%. The top and bottom plenums are assumed to be an extension of the filler bed, given an overall porosity of 51,2%. Fluid mixing phenomena at inlet/outlet zone of the storage are not simulated.

3.1.2.1 Simulation Results in Charge

Figure 10 shows simulated and experimental results of the charge run on 26/3/2021, with a mass flow of 0.45kg/s. Simulation data have been obtained using a modified Nusselt number ($Nu_{\text{modified}} = Nu \cdot 3$) and increasing the overall storage capacity by 20%. Although overall behaviour shows good agreement with experimental results, mismatches in the temperature profiles are observed, being significant at the top of tank. This discrepancy may be because top/bottom fluid zones are simulated by considering common porosity of 51.2%.

Figure 10: Charge from 180°C to 250°C with mass flow of 0.45 kg/s (Experiment on 26.03.21)

Figure 11: Comparison of simulated and experimental outlet temperature

3.2 CONCLUSIONS

- In terms of heat transfer, storage has different behaviour in charge and discharge cycles.
- The correlation proposed by Gnielinski for solid to liquid heat transfer has to be increased by a factor of 3 at charge and of 4 at discharge

4. CIEMAT SIMULATION MODEL

In order to simulate and understand the expected behaviour of Polyphem thermocline storage, CIEMAT has worked on two different approaches:

- a numerical model, where an effective unique medium is considered, it is 1 dimensional and thermal heat losses are considered negligible;
- an analytical method, where, the experimental thermocline profile is obtained. It is also a tool that either from experimental data or numerical simulation results, the main temperature profile features and effective properties are obtained and can be easily used within a pretty much complex simulation model that includes both energy source and sink, in annual simulations.

4.1 NUMERICAL METHOD: PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL APPROACH

The one-dimension (1D) differential energy balance equation that describes the behaviour of a thermocline storage tank with a single effective storage medium and for which thermal losses can be neglected is:

$$(\rho c_p)_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_f c_{p,f} v \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = k_{eff} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad \text{Eq.(15)}$$

where ρ , c_p and k stand for the density, specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity, subscript 'eff' refers to the effective medium, v is the fluid seepage velocity¹, T is the temperature of both solid and fluid –it is assumed to be the same for both media- and x' and t' are the dimensional space and time variables. This is to be solved in a system with height L ($0 < x < L$).

It is assumed that

$$(\rho c_p)_{eff} = \varepsilon \rho_f c_{p,f} + (1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s c_{p,s} \quad \text{and} \quad k_{eff} = \varepsilon k_f \zeta + (1 - \varepsilon) k_s \quad \text{Eq.(16)}$$

where 's' refers to solid and 'f' refers to fluid, ε represents the porosity of the storage medium and the coefficient ζ represents the correction for thermal dispersion in a porous medium. Thermal dispersion is a complex phenomenon which accounts for the heat transfer due to hydrodynamic mixing of the interstitial fluid at the pore scale. Correlations for this coefficient ζ are not easy to find. Following Catton et al (1998) results for packed bed with uniform spherical beads, we assume that:

$$\zeta = \frac{\dot{m}_0 d_p c_f}{k_f (1 - \varepsilon) \pi} \frac{2B}{\pi} \quad \text{Eq.(17)}$$

where d_p is the spherical particle diameter, $B = 1.75$ is a constant and \dot{m}_0 is the inlet fluid mass flow rate, $\dot{m}_0 = \rho_f v A$, with A the tank cross sectional area.

Boundary and initial conditions for the energy equation are:

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0: \quad & \rho_f c_{p,f} v T - \zeta_0 [\varepsilon k_f \zeta + (1 - \varepsilon) k_s] \partial T / \partial x = \rho_f c_{p,f} v T_{in}, \\ x = L: \quad & \partial T / \partial x = 0, \\ t = 0: \quad & T = T_0, \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq.(18)}$$

Note that $\rho_f v$, or rather, the fluid mass entering the tank, \dot{m}_0 ($\dot{m}_0 = \rho_f v A$), the temperature of the fluid entering

⁽¹⁾ Seepage velocity is the one considering the whole porous medium volume. Actual velocity is higher than seepage by a factor $1/\varepsilon$

the tank, T_{in} , and the initial temperature of the tank, T_0 , are the operational parameters. The parameter ζ_0 appearing in the boundary condition at $x' = 0$ describes the effect of additional (turbulence-induced) diffusion at the inlet.

We can define the dimensionless parameters θ , x and t (temperature, space and time, respectively) as:

$$\theta = \frac{(T - T_0)}{(T_{in} - T_0)}; \quad x' = \frac{x}{L}; \quad t' = \frac{\rho_f c_f v t}{[\epsilon \rho_f c_f + (1 - \epsilon) \rho_s c_s] L}$$

and write the dimensionless version of the energy equation:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t'} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x'} = \frac{1}{Pe} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x'^2} \quad \text{Eq.(19)}$$

with boundary and initial conditions:

$$x' = 0: \phi - \zeta_0 (Pe)^{-1} \partial \phi / \partial x' = 1,$$

$$x' = 1: \partial \phi / \partial x' = 0,$$

$$t' = 0: \phi = 0,$$

and with $Pe = \frac{L \rho_f c_{p,f} v}{[\epsilon k_f \zeta + (1 - \epsilon) k_s]}$, being the Peclet number.

4.1.1 Applying Model to Polyphem

Applying the above model to POLYPHEM, we can associate the required spherical particle diameter, d_p , to the mean solid thickness between the hollows of the bricks, i.e., $d_p = 0.0125 \text{ m}$. The volume to be simulated is the one named as Filler Bed, so a value of the porosity of $\epsilon = 0.33$ has been applied (Figure in **Table 1**).

Comparing numerical versus experimental results show that the best fitting is obtained assuming $\zeta_0 = \zeta$ in Eq.(17). Inlet temperature has been considered the mean experimental value of thermocouple named as T6.7.

It seems that to have a good overlap of the experimental and numerical curves, the total mass flow rate through the porous medium should be reduced. This can be attributed to the fact that not all of the liquid passes through the porous medium and some of the liquid seeps between the baskets and the walls of the device, thereby reducing the effective filtration rate through the Filler Bed.

While for low mass flow a good agreement both in advance velocity and thickness of the thermocline region is obtained (see **Figure 12**), poorer results are obtained while increasing the mass flow. An important delay is observed between the simulated and experimental data for the test on 7/4/2021, with a 0.9kg/s mass flow (Figure 13). The simulation results in **Figure 14** are obtained using the total experimental mass flow (without artificial reduction). For this case, the value of the coefficient ζ_0 used in the boundary conditions was nevertheless reduced to $\zeta_0 = 100$ which is less than the value $\zeta = 290$ used in the governing equation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: Experimental (lines with circles) versus simulated temperature profiles. (a) $T_0=180^\circ\text{C}$; $T_{in}=244^\circ\text{C}$; mean experimental mean mass flow 0.2kg/s , while simulations are obtained with a mass flow of 0.17kg/s ; (b) $T_0=200^\circ\text{C}$; $T_{in}=244^\circ\text{C}$; mean experimental mean mass flow 0.2kg/s , while simulations are obtained with 0.155kg/s ;

(a)

(b)

Figure 13: Experimental (lines with circles) versus simulated temperature profiles. (a) $T_0=180^\circ\text{C}$; $T_{in}=250^\circ\text{C}$; mean experimental mean mass flow 0.3kg/s , while simulations are obtained with a mass flow of 0.25kg/s ; $\zeta=80$ according to Eq.(37); (b) $T_0=200^\circ\text{C}$; $T_{in}=245^\circ\text{C}$; mean experimental mean mass flow 0.45kg/s , while simulations are obtained with a mass flow of 0.42kg/s ; $\zeta=140$ according to Eq.(37)

Figure 14: Experimental versus numerical results for 07/04/2021: Mass flow used in simulations of 0.9kg/s , i.e. no reduction in mass flow and dispersion coefficient of $\zeta=290$ (Eq.(17))

4.2 ANALYTICAL METHOD:

This method is a tool to analyse experimental data to see what is the advance velocity of the thermocline, v_{TC}

The exact solution of Eq.(15) can be approximated by different functions, between which the generalized logistic function is. Therefore, experimental data has been fitted using a logistic function of the type

$$\phi_{x_i}(t) = \phi_{min} + \frac{(\phi_{max} - \phi_{min})}{(1 + M e^{-B(t-t_c)})^n} \quad \text{Eq.(20)}$$

Where x_i , is a specific location given by the different thermocouples locations of the non-dimensional temperature profile, ϕ_{x_i} at time t . The fitting is applied using time as independent variable since the available experimental data is much larger than if the fitting was on the positions, since it would be limited to the number of thermocouples. t_c is the time corresponding to the inflection point of the sigmoidal curve, B is a parameter associated to the curve slope in that point and both M and n are parameters that should have the same value for a certain test, independently of the specific position, x_i , the fitting curve is referred to. Since t_c is the inflection point of the non-dimensional curve for a specific location, x_i , its value must correspond to the time at which the 1st non-dimensional temperature derivative becomes null. Once this t_c is found, imposing the mentioned condition for M and n , the values required for Eq.(20) are obtained. It is interesting to note that both M and n have been found to be different for charge and discharge processes.

Charge	Discharge
M=0,1	M=2
n=10	n=0,45

Table 4. M and n values of the generalized logistic functions used for charge and discharge processes

Examples of the applied fitting for a charge (26th of March) and a discharge (14th of April) processes are displayed in **Figure 15**. The fitting parameter for all the experimental data obtained at MicroSol test facility is always above 0.999, which is a clear value of the good fitting with this approach.

Figure 15. Fitting of the experimental temperature-time curves by using generalized logistic functions

When considering all the set of temperature-time curves in a specific test and plotting at which tank height t_c is allocated, the experimental thermocline velocity (v_{TC}) can be calculated as the slope of the clearly linear adjustment of such values (see **Figure 16**). In a charging, t_c moves down while in a discharging it moves up. The linear adjustment of all the experiments has always an R^2 factor above 0.998.

Figure 16. Linear plots of x vs. t_c for calculating the experimental v_{TC}

In **Table 5** the so obtained v_{TC} values (named as $v_{TC-z&t_c}$) are recorded for all charge tests that have been analysed and in **Table 6** for all the discharge tests. A column shows in **Table 5** the mass flow ($\dot{m}_{0,vTC-z&t_c}$) that would correspond to this thermocline velocity, v_{TC} , since

$$v_{TC} = \frac{\rho_l c_{p,l}}{(\rho c_p)_{eff}} \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_l 0,25\pi D^2} = \frac{c_{p,l} \dot{m}}{(\rho c_p)_{eff} 0.25\pi D^2} \quad \text{Eq.(21)}$$

using the entire tank diameter, $D=0.1276\text{m}$, so porosity is assumed to be 0.443 (see **Figure 7**).

Table 5: Mass flow, working temperatures and experimental v_{TC} values for all the MicroSol charge tests analysed, ordered by mass flow and temperature range

Date	$\dot{m}_{0,Exp}$ (kg/s)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	$v_{TC-z&t_c}$ (m/s)	$\dot{m}_{0,vTC-z&t_c}$ (kg/s)	$(\dot{m}_{0,Exp} - \dot{m}_{0,vTC-z&t_c})$ (%)	$\dot{m}_{0,simulation}$ (kg/s)
15-mar-21	0,2	175	100	1,12E-04	0,170	15%	
25-mar-21	0,2	250	180	1,20E-04	0,182	9%	0,17
01-abr-21	0,2	250	200	1,20E-04	0,182	9%	0,16
17-feb-21	0,3	160	100	1,35E-04	0,199	34%	
11-mar-21	0,3	175	100	1,68E-04	0,255	15%	
15-abr-21	0,3	250	180	1,92E-04	0,302	-1%	0,25
13-abr-21	0,3	300	220	1,92E-04	0,292	3%	
08-mar-21	0,4	175	100	2,28E-04	0,346	13%	
09-mar-21	0,4	175	100	2,27E-04	0,345	14%	
02-mar-21	0,44	160	100	2,48E-04	0,368	16%	
19-feb-21	0,45	160	100	2,43E-04	0,369	18%	
23-feb-21	0,45	160	100	2,48E-04	0,377	16%	
04-mar-21	0,45	200	135	2,57E-04	0,390	13%	
26-mar-21	0,45	245	180	2,72E-04	0,413	8%	0,42
31-mar-21	0,6	200	130	3,47E-04	0,527	12%	
07-abr-21	0,87	250	180	5,62E-04	0,853	2%	
24-mar-21	0,94	180	100	3,88E-04	0,589	37%	

Table 6: Mass flow, working temperatures and experimental v_{TC} values for all the MicroSol discharge tests analysed. Ordered by mass flow and temperature range

Date	Mass flow (kg/s)	T_{max} (°C)	T_{min} (°C)	$v_{TC-z\&tc}$ (m/s)	$\dot{m}_{0,vTC-z\&tc}$ (kg/s)	$(\dot{m}_{0,Exp} - \dot{m}_{0,vTC-z\&tc})$ (%)
06-may-21	0,15	280	155	9,17E-05	0,139	7%
27-abr-21	0,15	290	140	8,50E-05	0,129	14%
20-abr-21	0,2	260	130	1,17E-04	0,178	11%
30-abr-21	0,2	265	130	1,17E-04	0,178	11%
22-abr-21	0,2	290	135	1,18E-04	0,179	10%
14-abr-21	0,3	300	160	1,82E-04	0,276	8%
12-mar-21	0,39	170	110	2,32E-04	0,352	10%
10-mar-21	0,4	165	110	2,37E-04	0,360	10%
23-mar-21	0,6	180	110	3,52E-04	0,534	11%
31-mar-21	0,88	250	130	5,45E-04	0,827	6%
22-mar-21	0,91	180	110	5,52E-04	0,838	8%

The oil mass flows corresponding to thermocline velocity obtained from experimental data inflexion point, $\dot{m}_{0,vTC-z\&tc}$, is always lower (3%-37%) than the one reported to be imposed experimentally, but experiments on 15/4/2021. This fact additionally supports the hypothesis on using a lower mass flow in simulations (shown in the last column of **Table 5**) than the one reported experimentally to fit experimental data. With the exception of the test on 24th March (charge), the difference between the experimental oil mass flow and the one obtained by experimental thermocline velocity is around 10%, which is a common value for the uncertainty of mass flow meters.

4.3 CONCLUSIONS

- Simulation results fit experimental data in the range [0.2, 0.45] kg/s slightly decreasing the mass flow and considering a similar thermal dispersion effect both at the inlet boundary condition and in the diffusive term. The higher the mass flow in this range, the poorer the agreement is.
- Decreasing the mass flow for simulating just the filler bed has sense because there is some mass flow which goes easier between the inner tank walls and the filler, decreasing the available oil flow through the filler to be taken into account in the simulations.
- From the experimental temperature profile how the thermocline front advances can be known. An analytical procedure has been proposed. This analysis shows that the experimental mass flow should be decreased around 10% to fix the experimental evolution of temperatures. This decrease is in range of most 'mass flow meters' accuracy and in accordance with the obtained simulation results.
- This analysis questions that the test on 24th March is being recorded appropriately.
- Discharge processes have not been simulated.

5. COMPARISON BETWEEN MODELS

Each partner follows a 1-D approach to simulate the behaviour of a storage tank with structured filler as the Polyphem TES system has, but with the following differences:

- While CEA and F-ISE distinguish between solid and HTF temperature (and heat balances), CIEMAT does not, assuming an effective medium which accounts for both the solid and HTF contributions.
- CEA and F-ISE models use a similar heat transfer coefficients between solid and HTF, since although CEA uses Wakao correlation and F-ISE a modified Gnielinski's correlation, the absolute values finally obtained are similar in both models.
- F-ISE includes a heat energy balance for the tank walls as a third equation to solve.
- CEA and F-ISE simulation models account for thermal losses to ambient, calculated theoretically considering different materials in series. CEA model includes these thermal losses in the liquid energy balance equation while F-ISE includes them in the wall energy balance equation. CIEMAT's model neglects thermal losses.
- CEA and F-ISE simulation models consider thermophysical properties of the fluid variable with temperature, while CIEMAT's model considers them constant.
- While CEA and F-ISE impose as boundary condition at the inlet of the fluid a fixed temperature (either the maximum one in charge or the minimum one in discharge), CIEMAT imposes that the temperature at this inlet does not vary with time, so a diffusivity equation is established as boundary condition.
- CEA's model considers the thermal inertia given by the oil volume above and below the filler
- CIEMAT's model includes thermal dispersion, i.e., heat transfer due to hydrodynamic mixing of the interstitial fluid at the pore scale.

Although further research is required some common conclusions can be identified:

- Charging processes around the mass flow range 0.45 kg/s can be accurately simulated by any of the simulation models here proposed.
- Not all the oil to solid heat transfer correlations proposed in the literature for random packed beds are applicable to structured filler. In that sense, Wakao's correlation seems to be appropriate.
- Oil to solid heat transfer is somehow enhanced in discharging in comparison with charging.

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